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LIBRARY LEADERS: CONCEPTS AND TRAITS

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Many leaders are competent, but few qualify as remarkable. If you want to join the ranks of the best of the best, make sure you embody all these qualities all the time. It isn't easy, but the rewards can be truly phenomenal. Library leaders should be striving to be “great” leaders. It's what the profession needs to flourish in the ambiguous future and regain the library's relevance in the community. It is what's needed for survival. Mainly nine traits as given-

1. Awareness
2. Decisiveness
3. Empathy
4. Accountability
5. Confidence
6. Optimism
7. Honesty
8. Focus
9. Inspiration

DEFINITION LEADERSHIP

Leadership is a reciprocal process of motivating individuals and mobilizing resources in pursuit of goals shared by members of a group, organization, or community. As an aspect of group innovation and problem-solving behavior, leadership involves the clarification of group goals, the communication of strategies for goal achievement, the initiation of structure in interaction and expectation, and the assumption of responsibility for results. Leadership in libraries can have many different faces and does not require that you supervise people in your paid position.

Main traits as given-

Great Leaders Have High Character

Think about a situation in which you knew you could do something and no one would EVER know about it if you didn't tell. Good or bad, doesn't matter, your actions would never be found out. There would be no evidence of your actions linked to you. There would be no repercussions to you or anyone you knew. That's not to say that your actions would have no impact on anyone, actions always have impact on someone or something, just no one you know who could trace your actions back to you. What would you do? The answer to this question is what constitutes a person's character.

Great Leaders Are Visionary

We all know that Jules Vern was a highly imaginative guy. But my bet is he took a few ideas from Leonardo De Vinci – the guy who envisioned the helicopter and parachute – in the middle ages. I think Walt Disney must have taken after them to create his magical kingdoms, and so many others must have also had vision to be able to create monumental dams and bridges, space ships, computers, artificial limbs, and medical marvels of all kinds. I suspect Vern was hoping that someone would achieve and make real what he only dreamed, and they did. A great leader has the vision that, with his/her leadership ability, will influence others to make real.

Great Leaders Take Responsibility

Responsibility is a fundamental human trait that allows organizations to function. Individuals who recognize a responsibility to do their best, as well as see what needs to be done and take responsibility to get it done, are the life's blood of any library. Having a sense of responsibility motivates people to do the right things, it is the cause of much of the world's successes, and lack of it the cause of much of the world's problems. A great leader takes responsibility for everything his/her library does, or fails to do. No IF's, AND's or BUT's about it. The buck stops at the library director's desk.

Great Leaders Are Decision Makers

How often have you been faced with a problem that needed solving, but you either weren't sure how to tackle it, or didn't think you had time to tackle it right then, or for whatever reason just put it off. What usually happens? The problem gets worse. It never fails. Problems do not fix themselves, regardless of what some people say. It is true that 'No decision is a decision.' If you put something off long enough circumstances will decide for you, and often times that decision is not a desirable one. Life's experience has shown most of us to address problems as soon as they are recognized, to prevent them from becoming much bigger, and to solve them sooner rather than later. Great leaders just do it!

Great Leaders Are Problem Solvers

Understanding the problem is essential to solving the problem. Identifying the problem correctly helps one narrow it to the point of being able to solve it, because we can usually see the solution if we can grasp the problem. How often have we heard something like – 'That's great, but you solved the wrong problem.' – whether it was regarding a school math question, or taking care of business? Understanding the problem correctly is the key to solving any problem. And, here we see again, one of the qualities of leadership is solving problems before they get totally out of hand. Combine responsibility with problem solving and great leaders get things done!

Great Leaders Are Learners

It has been relatively recent, maybe 20 years at most, that business and most other public endeavors have encouraged life-long learning as an important factor of success in today's society. With the proliferation of technology our society has transitioned to a 'trial and error' method of learning. We learn to use technology by playing with it, using it to do whatever we think it will do, and learning how to make it work. However, the great leader is an active learner, seeking professional development opportunities, listening to people, especially employees, and assimilating knowledge for the purpose of becoming a better decision maker, and a better leader.

Great Leaders Delegate and Empower

Delegation is not the same as empowerment. Delegating authority to accomplish a job is routine and generally pertains to the specifics of that job. Empowerment means giving employees the authority to step outside their specific job duties to enable them to accomplish other tasks that are at the core of the organization's values. For example, it would not be considered normal for a cataloger to be empowered to take steps to ensure the highest quality customer service. That is generally reserved to reference staff and youth services librarians and others who deal directly with the customer. But why shouldn't every employee of the library be empowered to ensure that every customer is totally satisfied with their experience at the library in every respect? Great leaders not only delegate, but empower everyone to make the library more than it can ever be without their contributions.

Great Leaders Understand Motivation

What motivates you? Probably many things, including a belief in what you do as something worth doing. Money? Sociologists suggest that money is not a motivator, but lack of it can be a de-motivator. Praise? Everyone likes praise, unless they believe it is given without sincerity. Hope? Concerning working in a library, the best motivation is the intrinsic value of the work itself. Great leaders recognize each employee's motivators and tries to ensure that they fulfill those for all employees. Motivation takes many forms.

Great Leaders Express Gratitude

A great leader will never miss the opportunity to show appreciation for someone's efforts, and successes. The power of appreciation is strong, and as noted below, can be a strong motivator. Studies have shown that the number one reason why people leave an organization is lack of appreciation. It's not money, it's failure on the part of the leader to make the employee feel valued and recognized for the work they do. Criticism seems to be the easiest thing in the world to give, but encouragement is something a great leader does not have to work at doing.

Great Leaders Do Not Do It Alone

Whenever someone thinks one member of the team is a super star, it's best to remember that EVERY true leader requires followers, and not just followers, but individuals who can and

will comprise a team. The most heavy lifting is done by a team. The best work is accomplished by a team that believes in the library and owns the vision. I suspect that life has shown us all that although we like to think we're indispensable, once we've left an organization, life goes on and work continues in whatever new direction it will, doing quite well without us.

Bass' Theory of Leadership

Bass' theory of leadership states that there are three basic ways to explain how people become leaders (Stogdill, 1989; Bass, 1990). The first two explain the leadership development for a small number of people, while the third one is the dominant theory today. These theories are:

- Some personality traits may lead people naturally into leadership roles. This is the Trait Theory.
- A crisis or important event may cause a person to rise to the occasion, which brings out extraordinary leadership qualities in an ordinary person. This is the Great Events Theory.
- People can choose to become leaders. People can learn leadership skills. This is the Transformational or Process Leadership Theory. It is the most widely accepted theory today and the premise on which this leadership guide is based.

Management verses Leadership

While management and leadership have a great deal in common, such as working with people and accomplishing the goals of the organization, they do differ in their primary functions (Kotter, 1990):

Management's main function is to produce order and consistency through processes, such as planning, budgeting, organizing, staffing, and problem solving.

While **leadership's** main function is to produce movement and constructive or adaptive change through processes, such as establishing direction through visioning, aligning people, motivating, and inspiring.

For more information on the differences between management and leadership see the next chapter: The Four Pillars: Leadership, Management, Command, and Control

Boss or Leader?

Although your position as a manager, supervisor, lead, etc. gives you the authority to accomplish certain tasks and objectives in the organization (, this *power* does not make you a leader, it simply makes you a *boss*. Leadership differs in that it makes the followers *want* to achieve high goals, rather than simply ordering people around. Thus, you get *Assigned Leadership* by your position and you display *Emergent Leadership* by influencing people to do great things.

Total Leadership

What makes a person want to follow a leader? People want to be guided by leaders they respect and who have a clear sense of direction. To gain respect, they must be ethical. A sense of direction is achieved by conveying a strong vision of the future.

When people are deciding if they respect you as a leader, they do not think about your attributes, rather, they observe what you *do* so that they can determine who you really *are*. They use this observation to tell if you are an honorable and trusted leader or a self-serving person who misuses authority to look good and get promoted.

Self-serving leaders are not as effective because their employees only obey them, not follow them. They succeed in many areas because they present a good image to their seniors... but at the expense of their workers.

Good leadership is honorable character and selfless service to your organization. In your employees' eyes, your leadership is everything you do that effects the organization's objectives and their well-being.

The Two Most Important Keys to Effective Leadership

- Trust and confidence in top leadership was the single most reliable predictor of employee satisfaction in an organization.

- Effective communication by leadership in three critical areas was the key to winning organizational trust and confidence:
 - Helping employees understand the company's overall business strategy.
 - Helping employees understand how they contribute to achieving key business objectives.
 - Sharing information with employees on both how the company is doing and how an employee's own division is doing.

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